

Schiff Base Complexes of Antimony(III) and (V) Chlorides

T. N. SRIVASTAVA, A. K. S. CHAUHAN and H. N. MEHROTRA

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow, India

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The direct interaction of antimony tri- and pentachloride with salicylideneaniline and its amine ring substituted derivatives results in the formation of adducts with 1:1 stoichiometry. The newly synthesized compounds have been characterized through elemental analysis, conductance measurement and infrared data. It is concluded that the ligands coordinate to the metal atom through their azomethine nitrogen giving rise to four- and six-coordinated antimony complexes.

THE adduct-forming tendency of salicylideneanilines towards various transition and non-transition metal halides has been investigated¹⁻⁵. Recently, Singh and Tandon^{6,7} studied the reaction of antimony(III) isopropoxide with Schiff bases containing one o-OH group either in aldehyde or amine fragment and obtained chelates of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 stoichiometries where the bases in their anionic form behave as bidentate ligands.

The Lewis acidity of both trivalent and pentavalent antimony chloride is well known⁸ and molecular complexes with benzylideneanilines have been reported⁹. It was considered of interest to study the behaviour of these chlorides towards aromatic Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde in which the electron density at the azomethine nitrogen atom is disturbed owing to the formation of a quasi aromatic ring by intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The present communication reports the interaction of SbCl₃ and SbCl₅ with the following Schiff bases

R = H(L-1); *p*-CH₃(L-2);
p-Cl(L-3);
p-OCH₃(L-4);
p-NO₂(L-5) and
m-NO₂(L-6)

Experimental

Anhydrous antimony trichloride (Albright and Wilson, UK) and pentachloride (Allied Chemicals, USA) were distilled under reduced pressure before use. The Schiff bases were prepared by the direct condensation of salicylaldehyde with aniline and its ring substituted derivatives in ethanol; the yellow to red compounds were recrystallized from the same solvent.

The molecular adducts were obtained by the direct interaction of antimony chlorides and Schiff bases in a dry inert solvent under nitrogen. In a typical experiment 5m moles (1.14 g) of SbCl₃ in 25 ml dry benzene were added dropwise to a solution of salicylideneaniline (4 g, more than 10 m moles) in the same solvent under

stirring in an atmosphere of dry nitrogen. A sticky mass appeared almost instantaneously. The mixture was stirred for an hour to ensure complete precipitation and then refluxed on a water bath for 30 minutes which yielded a crystalline product. It was filtered, washed with the same solvent and dried in vacuum. The reactions of SbCl₅ were carried out in dichloromethane without refluxing.

The complexes were analysed for antimony. A weighed sample of the compound was decomposed with a mixture of conc. H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ and heated to remove nitric acid. The resulting antimony solution was reduced with sulphurous acid and Sb(III) precipitated as sulphide. The precipitate after filtration was dissolved in conc. HCl and titrated against a standard solution of potassium bromate¹⁰. The analytical data are reported in the table. The conductance measurements were made using a Phillips PR9500 conductivity bridge in nitrobenzene at 30°. The molar conductance values are listed in the table. The infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded using Perkin Elmer 157 spectrophotometer in KBr discs. The relevant frequencies along with their assignments are given.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are intense yellow to red coloured solid, insoluble in common organic solvents excepting methanol and nitrobenzene and have sharp melting point. The analytical data show that the bases form adducts of 1:1 stoichiometry, in which they behave as neutral monodentate ligands coordinated to antimony atom irrespective of its oxidation state. Molar conductance values of the adducts suggest them to be non-electrolytes.

A critical comparison of the spectra of the free Schiff bases with those of the corresponding complexes, enables to draw certain conclusions concerning absorptions of diagnostic value. In the spectra of ligands the broad weak band centred around 2800 cm⁻¹ is characteristic of intramolecularly H-bonded OH group¹¹. On complexation this band is shifted

TABLE—EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR SbCl_3 AND SbCl_5 ADDUCTS WITH THE SCHIFF BASES

Compound	m. p. °C	Elemental Analysis % Found (Calcd.) Sb	C	H	Molar Conductance (ohm ⁻¹ cm ³ mole ⁻¹)	IR frequencies (cm ⁻¹)* $\nu(\text{OH})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$
$\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{L} - 1$	155	29.02 (28.62)	37.14 (36.71)	2.58 (2.61)	6.25	2900mbr	1635m
$\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{L} - 2$	172	27.19 (27.71)	38.73 (38.27)	2.83 (2.98)	4.09	3000m	1640s
$\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{L} - 3$	181	26.79 (26.48)	33.54 (33.96)	2.30 (2.19)	3.12	2975m	1638s
$\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{L} - 4$	165	26.53 (26.74)	37.28 (36.93)	2.84 (2.88)	6.90	3025w	1642vs
$\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{L} - 5$	142	26.37 (25.89)	33.62 (33.20)	2.37 (2.14)	3.70	2950mbr	1640vs
$\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{L} - 6$	145	26.22 (25.89)	33.14 (33.20)	2.23 (2.14)	7.04	2950 wbr	1635w
$\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{L} - 1$	180d	24.89 (24.53)	31.25 (31.46)	2.41 (2.23)	8.23	3100m	1637vs
$\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{L} - 2$	190	24.41 (23.86)	32.54 (32.95)	2.56 (2.57)	6.30	3090w	1638s
$\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{L} - 3$	208d	22.98 (22.94)	29.76 (29.42)	2.18 (1.90)	5.30	3125mbr	1635m
$\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{L} - 4$	170	23.57 (23.13)	31.67 (31.95)	2.37 (2.49)	5.83	3100m	1640vs
$\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{L} - 5$	198	22.83 (22.49)	29.15 (28.85)	1.97 (1.86)	3.15	3100w	1636vs
$\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{L} - 6$	195	22.91 (22.49)	29.29 (28.85)	2.07 (1.86)	5.72	3150w	1638m

* br = broad, m = medium, s = strong, v = very, w = weak.

to ~ 3000 and ~ 3100 cm^{-1} in adducts of SbCl_3 and SbCl_5 respectively. It is, therefore, inferred that the closed ring due to intramolecular H-bonding is retained in all the complexes in distorted form; the extent of distortion being more in adducts of SbCl_5 than that in those of SbCl_3 . This is in agreement with the earlier observations made by Tanaka *et al*¹². Furthermore, the strong band appearing in the spectra of the ligands around 1280 cm^{-1} due to phenolic C-O stretching mode¹³ shows negligible shift upon complexation and makes us believe that *o*-hydroxy group of the bases has not taken part in complex formation. The analytical data support the above conclusion.

The main indication of the formation of molecular complexes through infrared spectral data is an increase in the C=N stretching frequency, which suggests coordination of the Schiff bases through the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group. In accordance with the published data^{14,15} stretching vibrations of the $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ group in free salicylideneanilines are known to absorb in the range 1603 - 1622 cm^{-1} . In the spectra of the adduct studied here this band is shifted to

1638 ± 5 cm^{-1} . Similar observations are also reported for adducts of TiCl_4 and SnCl_4 with these bases¹⁶. The increase of $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ during coordination may be due to the unshared pair of electrons at the nitrogen atom being attracted to the antimony atom, the n, π conjugation with the aniline ring is broken down and a partial positive charge is produced at the nitrogen atom. This hinders the usual π, π conjugation of the azomethine group with the aniline nucleus. The removal of the azomethine group from the conjugation and its electronic structure analogous to the structure of the protonated group $-\text{CH}=\text{N}^+\text{H}-$ increase the frequency of its absorption in the infrared spectra^{1,17}.

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